

iJEResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Dec, 2021 | Peer-Reviewed Journal
ISSN 27649733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10573651

ACCEPTANCE, FAMILY AND RESPECT – THE SEARCH WAS NEVER FOR TOLERANCE. AN INTEGRATIVE REVIEW APPLIED TO PUBLIC HEALTH

Author: Romero Vieira Vasconcelos

ABSTRACT : Even today, homosexuality is a controversial subject, generating diverse opinions among scholars in the area, in which it is possible to identify the existing risks and barriers that homosexual faces when revealing his homosexuality in the family and social sphere, since many times there may be negative consequences, such as family contempt, depression, homophobia, among others. The objective of the present study is to identify and describe the scientific evidence about family and social acceptance regarding homosexual orientation. It is an integrative review of literature in the scielo , lilacs and bdenf databases, presenting researches between the period from 1999 to 2017. The results point out the difficulties of accepting the family and the society when it comes to homosexuality, and can generate internal and external conflicts when not in this respect, the consequences can generate harm to the homosexual such as risk of suffering homophobia, prejudice, rejection by various environments.

Keywords: Homosexuality. Family relationships. Tolerance.

INTRODUCTION

To talk about homosexuality, it must be necessary to talk about sexuality, whose concept is a little complicated, as it involves a series of factors, such as behavior, the sexual act, notions of what is masculine and feminine and sexual orientation, the latter being the theme of the present work.

Homosexuality in ancient Greece and Rome was considered natural, as there was already the existence of homosexual relationships, where the cult of beauty was practiced in which older men gathered in a gymnasium to appreciate the physical beauty of young people who remained naked. However, it was not called homosexuality, because what predominated was bisexuality, since men joined women in order to reproduce, in which heterosexual relationships began to predominate, and then marriage and family emerged (MOREIRA, MARTINS, 2008).

With the end of the Roman Empire in 533 BC with Justinian there was a complete change in the direction of homosexuality, where it was punished with burning and castration, claiming that homosexual practice was not a practice accepted by God. Thus arising the non-acceptance of male homosexuality.

It is justified that, for a better understanding of homosexuality, the definition of sexual orientation is distinguished, which is the ability to develop, have or feel attraction or sexual, emotional or affective relationship with other people. Being subdivided into: Heterosexual: person who feels attraction or relates to people of the opposite sex. Bisexual: A person who is attracted to or has relationships with people of both sexes. Homosexual: person who is attracted to or has relationships with people of the same sex, where homosexual women are called lesbians, homosexual men are called gays. (BRAZIL, 2016).

The International Association of Gays, Lesbians, Bisexuals, Transsexuals and Intersexuals (ILGA), reinforce that the definition for homophobia is fear, aversion or discrimination against homosexuality, being also characterized as hatred, hostility or disapproval of the same. In 2007, around

85 member states of the United Nations still criminalize homosexual relationships, making the culture of hate official, where the homosexual population needs to hide out of fear, in which the prevailing culture related to hate and violence are accepted by the state, forcing this population into invisibility and self-denial (OTTOSSON, 2007).

In 1894, the term Homosexuality was used for the first time in Brazil by Francisco José Viveiros de Castro in the book "indecent assault: studies on aberrations of the sexual instinct". In the late 1970s and early 1980s, during the military dictatorship, social movements marked history not only in the search for democracy but for civil rights and citizenship, thus starting the construction of movements, also making visible the construction of gay movements.

With this, the first gay movement in Brazil emerged in 1979 in São Paulo and the first Brazilian meeting of homosexuals was held the following year. Starting an incessant fight for the end of discrimination and prejudice, that is, a fight against the so ingrained homophobia present visibly and invisibly in our society (PAGANO, 2011).

As a problem, it is seen that, despite the difficulties in finding statistical data, studies indicate that the percentage of homosexuals is represented by about 3% to 10% of the population (NOGUEIRA et al., 2012). In Brazil there are more than 60 thousand homosexual couples, whose region with the most homosexual couples is the Southeast, totaling 32,202 couples, followed by the Northeast with 12,196 couples. The South region has just over 8,000 homosexual couples, the Midwest with 4,141. And finally, the North region with the lowest number of homosexual couples totaled 3,429. (BRAZIL, 2010).

Despite advances in studies, homosexuality is still seen today as a sin, disease and crime, thus generating great rejection, discrimination from family members and society, people with homosexual orientation are found in all social environments, including socioeconomic groups, ethical and religious (MAGRINI et al., 2014).

People who are part of these groups of sexual diversity become frequent victims of prejudice and discrimination due to their choice of gender identity and/or sexual orientation. Homophobia, a term used to define the prejudice of those who are against homosexuality, is mainly marked by aggressive gestures, offensive words, looks and even physical aggression and murders. This act is considered as unhealthy hatred (PAGANO, 2011).

One of the main difficulties in relation to homophobia when it is present in the family, making it complex in some cases for the homosexual to reveal his orientation (ZUCCHI; GARCIA, 1999).

Faced with this question, there is the question of the problem: What scientific evidence about family and social acceptance of homosexual orientation ?

As a hypothesis, it is seen that when assuming homosexuality, the individual needs mainly family support, however, in some cases it ends up being more difficult , thus leading to a destabilization and distance from family members, sometimes causing the gay to end up in search of new family references, such as the family of friends for feeling rejected by their own family (GONSALVES; SILVA, 2013).

Parenteral rejection, acceptance difficulties and bullying are responsible for at least one third of adolescent suicide deaths related to orientation issues (NOGUEIRA et al., 2012).

Therefore, the objective of this article is to identify the scientific evidence about family and social acceptance of homosexual orientation . The specific objectives are to write the scientific evidence about family acceptance of the individual's sexual orientation ; to verify the challenges faced by homosexuals in the family environment; and finally, to analyze what kind of family and social acceptance of the homosexual orientation.

A problem of investigation, at times, is drawn from what was evidenced in the review of studies on the difficulty of accepting the family in homosexuality. Showing the

consequences for family rejection and society in general.

METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

The integrative review According to Soares et al., (2014) is considered a form of systematic review, it consists of a broad analysis of publications, in order to obtain data on a given topic. This type of research includes the analysis of relevant publications, allows the synthesis of published studies on the subject, can indicate knowledge gaps that need to be filled through new research, in addition to providing general conclusions regarding the area of study. In order to maintain standards of methodological rigor, some steps were followed.

The first was the delimitation of the research question, the second was the choice of databases, the third step was the selection of these studies for this, key information was extracted, considering the question proposed for the investigation, in addition to identifying the type of study, subjects involved in the research, the scenario and the objectives, for the conclusion of this stage and the formulation of the results of this review, it was decided to use spreadsheets in Microsoft Excel , in order to gather and systematize this information. The other steps or steps were: analysis of included studies and interpretation of results. Once the methodological steps for this type of study were defined, they were followed as follows:

- 1) Starting from the need to explore studies in national and international scientific literature with the proposed research question: family acceptance and society's respect for homosexuals?

- 2) As for sampling or search, this IR counted as inclusion criteria studies published with a time frame from 1999 to 2017. Justified because in 1999, resolution 01/99 was created, which defines the attitude of psychologists as unethical who treat homosexuality as a deviant behavior and disease.

For selection, we opted for articles with full texts, preferably published in scientific journals of Nursing, methodology containing the necessary data to obtain the levels of evidence and being a research with emphasis on the research question. As exclusion criteria, publications unavailable in full text or inaccessible link due to error and other forms of publication other than scientific articles were chosen.

Articles that do not parallel the research topic were also excluded. Review articles and experience reports were not used in this research. This fact constituted a limitation of the study, as some relevant subjects could be contained in these other types of publications, such as monographs, editorials, manuals, books, among others. Searches were restricted to the following descriptors: Homosexuality; Family, acceptance, rejection and homophobia.

This IR presents primary research on the topic addressed, we chose to carry out searches in journals indexed in the databases and libraries of: Scientific Electronic Library Online (SCIELO), Latin American and Caribbean Literature on Health Sciences (LILACS), Nursing Database (BDENF).

Initially, for the first round of searches, it was decided to cross the descriptor homosexuality and the words family is nursing, a total of 96 articles were found, 28 articles in SCIELO, 60 in LILACS, 8 in BDENF.

Continuing with the inclusion and exclusion criteria, we initially excluded 58 articles from the search, details shown in Table 01.

Table 01: Application of inclusion and exclusion criteria.

STAGE	CRITERIA / BASES	SCIELO	LILACS	BDENF
1	Descriptors used in the search	Homosexuality Family	Homosexuality Family	Homosexuality Nursing
two	Articles found	28	60	8
3	Articles with a year of publication prior to 1999	0	7	1
4	Full texts available	27	37	6
5	Repeated / Duplicate Articles	0	0	0

6	Experience reports and review articles	0	two	two
7	Articles outside the research topic	7	14	0
8	Total articles excluded	8	46	4
9	Total viable articles for next step	20	14	4

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2017.

It should be noted that after step three, a previous reading was carried out, where a total of 28 articles from the research were excluded at this stage, as they did not fit the search question and the scope of this research. For analysis and next steps, 10 articles were selected. Table 02 presents the composition of the sample.

Table 02: Composition of the sample – Characterization of the studies by: title, descriptors, year and place of publication.

TITLE	DESCRIPTORS	PLACE / YEAR
The Debate on Homosexuality Mediated by Social Representations: Homosexual and Heterosexual Perspectives.	Homosexuality; social representations; social recognition; causality.	Rio de Janeiro-RJ / 2006
Life trajectory of a homosexual: between silence and oppression.	Homosexuality. Sexual behavior. Nursing assessment research. Community health nursing. Nursing	Natal-RN / 2007
Personal and family experiences of female homosexuals.	Female homosexuality, personal and family experiences.	Maringá-PR / 2008
Sexuality and work: study on the discrimination of male homosexuals in the banking sector.	Discrimination, male homosexuals, public bank, private bank.	São Paulo-SP / 2010
Humanization in the reception of lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transvestites and transsexuals in primary care: bioethical reflections.	Reception; primary care; homosexuality; bioethics.	Recife-PE 2011
Suicide Ideas and Attempts in Adolescents with Hetero and Homoerotic Sexual Practices.	Homophobia; Suicide; Homosexuality; Adolescence; sexual identity; Violence.	São Paulo-SP / 2012
Family and sexual orientation: Difficulties in accepting male homosexuality.	Homosexuality, family, sexual orientation.	Barretos-SP / 2014
Between revealing and hiding: parents and children in the face of the discovery of homosexuality.	Young homosexuals; family; domestic violence, Brazil.	Rio de Janeiro-RJ / 2014
Mothers, Children and Homosexuality: Narratives of Acceptance.	Homosexuality, acceptance, son, mother.	Irati-PR / 2015
The impact of homophobia on the health of homosexual adolescents.	Adolescent Health. Violence. Homosexuality.	Ribeirão Preto-SP / 2015

Source: Prepared by the authors .

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proceeding with the presentation of the results of the selected publications, it was observed that most studies have a qualitative methodological approach in a total of 10 articles. The research attention scenario presented variation, the family scenario stands out, however, the social scenario is punctuated as something emerging.

As for the country of origin of the studies, Brazil was the highlight hosting the 10 studies. As for the year of publication, there is a greater concentration of articles in the year 2014 and 2015, with 2 publications each.

The most prominent journal in the area was: *Temas em Psicologia* with two articles. The other journals had one publication each.

As for the objective of the articles, most of them point to family acceptance, as shown in Table 01. In this perspective, the authors emphasize that the complete acceptance of parents towards children with homosexual orientation does not apply in all cases, given that for most homosexual people this acceptance is something out of their reality because it is not an easy transition on either side. After the revelation, the parents faced six stages, namely: discovery, mourning, denial, defense, conformation and, in some cases, acceptance (HAUER, SIQUEIRA, 2015).

Table 3 : Distribution of articles by author, objective and journal, on family acceptance and society's respect for homosexuals: an integrative review with implications for nursing.

AUTHOR/YEAR	OBJECTIVE	PERIODICAL
Scardua ; alves, (2006)	To study the representations of homosexuality among university students, according to sexual orientation and sex.	Psychology: Reflection and Criticism.
Albino et al., (2007)	Unveiling the world of the person affected by a sexually transmitted disease, more specifically in investigating the life trajectory of a homosexual.	Science, Care and Health.
Arial ; centenary, (2008)	To describe the personal and family experiences of female homosexuals.	Psychology in Study.
Garcia; Moulin, (2010)	To analyze possible forms of discrimination in the workplace directed towards homosexual male employees.	Public Administration Magazine.

Souza et al., (2011)	Reflect on how public health can use the Bioethics framework to base its practice and assistance in relation to ensuring a humanized reception for Lesbians, Gays, Bisexuals, Transvestites and Transsexuals (LGBT) in primary care health services.	UFPE nursing journal online.
Silva; Rondini, (2012)	It sought to know the associations between sexual orientation and suicide ideations and attempts.	Health and sexual society.
Magrini, et al., (2014)	To understand the experience of men with homosexual orientation and the construction of the meanings of homosexuality in their respective families of origin.	Subjects in Psychology.
Barcelona; Baptist, (2014)	It deals with the relationship between parents and children when faced with the social situation of the discovery of homosexuality.	Latin American Magazine.
Hauer; Siqueira, (2015)	Understand how the process of acceptance of a homosexual son or daughter by his mother takes place.	Subjects in Psychology.
Regis et al., (2015)	Understand how homophobia can influence the health of homosexual adolescents.	Anna Nery School.

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2017.

After a thorough reading and data collection of the articles included in the IR, we identified that:

There are indications that homosexuality has been present in the history of humanity and since primitive societies in all cultures. In which the first reports appeared around the third Egyptian dynasty, around 2,500 BC. At the time, some civilizations allowed relationships between men, adults and young people, as it was only considered repudiation when they threatened to subvert the social hierarchy. Over time, this situation was explained in different ways. However, with the arrival of the Judeo-Christian tradition, homosexuality was changed, starting to be conceived as a sin (ARIAL; CENTENARO, 2008).

In view of the religious situation, the practices considered homo-affective were highlighted by the bible, both in the Old and New Testaments, where these biblical texts refer to the manifestations of human sexuality, in which the texts only emphasize evidence regarding the male sexual option (ALBINO et al., 2007).

Each person has their sexuality constructed through biopsychosocial aspects, which are divided into four pillars, biological sex as male and female, sexual identity defined as male and female, sexual orientation being homosexual, heterosexual and bisexual, it is the psychological aspect being understood by behaviors, attitudes and feelings, identified in the third pillar of the biopsychosocial aspects, sexual orientation and understood individually by the desire of each being throughout life, this desire being represented as heterosexual: attraction to the opposite sex. Bisexual: attraction to both sexes. Homosexual: attraction to people of the same sex. Where there is a need to be accepted, recognized and understood in their specificities and social and family relationships (MAGRINI et al., 2014).

The term homosexuality, which is widely used today, originated in German in a pamphlet considered anonymous in 1869 (ALBINO et al., 2007).

However, from the 19th century onwards homosexuality was defined by doctors as a physiological disease, in the 20th century it came to be seen by psychology as a behavioral deviation from sexuality due to the introduction of the suffix ISM. In which it came to be defined as a psychopathological disease where it was published in 1984 in the 6th journal of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD), falling into the category of pathological personality. In Brazil, in the 1980s, the Federal Council of Medicine stopped classifying homosexuality as a category of deviation and sexual disorder, making code 302.0 of the international classification of diseases unusable.

In 1999, the federal council of psychology made official through resolution 01/99, in which the posture of psychologists who treat homosexuality as a behavioral deviation and disease is unethical, resulting in a decision by the World Health Organization (WHO), which stops considering homosexuality as a disease (ARRIAL, CENTENARO, 2008).

According to Hauer and Siqueira (2015), homosexuality is still seen with a certain repudiation even with the increase in social

visibility, causing greater difficulties mainly in the family environment, where the main part of the parents' desire when it comes to waiting for a child and that it is oriented as heterosexual, as it will be a "right and natural" gender. As a girl, she will wear pink, play with dolls and practice ballet, while the boy will wear blue, play with carts and attend soccer class, making it impossible for this orientation to be changed to homosexuality over the years.

Consequently, when parents are faced with a homosexual son or daughter, it ends up being something embarrassing for that family. Having as a consequence, the deviation of the plans prior to this revelation, generating then the fear of social and divine judgment where the family ends up looking for who to blame, thus generating parenteral homophobia.

Silva and Rondini (2012) reinforce that homosexuality has a different representation in each place, considering that revealing their homosexuality in the family and social context can result in several different situations, such as value and consequences.

Knowing that the "family of origin" has greater difficulty in accepting the homosexual orientation of their children, from then on it ends up generating a conflict on both sides, and actions of physical and verbal violence can occur. Being marked by fear, apprehension and uncertainty on both sides. There is also evidence of psychological violence that is experienced silently, causing serious damage to the victim, such as health problems, low performance and even suicide attempts (BARCELOS; BATISTA, 2014).

Many times the homosexual ends up being forced to live in society hiding their true sexual orientation, because they were raised by a heterosexist model, where parents end up inducing their children to believe that they will marry and form a family, making a search of a partner of the opposite sex so as not to go against the wishes of the parents. (SILVA; RONDINI, 2012).

In addition to family rejection, homosexuals also encounter barriers in society

through homophobia and discrimination. Homophobia is characterized by a set of negative symptoms, such as fear, annoyance, hatred and repudiation, and its forms of expression are through physical force, psychological, verbal and sexual aggression. Related to the power of gender in society. According to the Ministry of Health, in 2012, 4,851 cases of homophobia were registered, which demonstrates a problem of great magnitude in society. Being a homosexual teenager, the largest population considered vulnerable, because they are teenagers and because of the violence and exclusion they are exposed to (REGIS et al., 2015).

It is observed that prejudice and any form of negative mental perception towards individuals and socially inferior groups, as well as the social representations connected to such perceptions, which means the materialization in the concrete plane of relationships, which produce violation of the rights of individuals and groups related to homosexuals, the author states that most homosexuals tend to hide their sexuality in environments such as work, with the intention of avoiding any and all discriminatory acts. On the other hand, those who hide their sexual orientation manifest low psychological levels of well-being and life satisfaction (GARCIA; MOULIN, 2010).

Regis et al. (2015) emphasizes that male homosexuals are more prone to suffer any type of Physical or Verbal Violence or even homophobic acts than homosexual women, due to the heterosexist society, the main occurrences of homophobia and in school, family and social environments. The most prevalent and verbal violence in which society uses pejorative terms to offend homosexuals causing fear of exposing their sexuality, which often due to parenteral and social homophobia can result in suicide.

Finally, parenteral rejection, acceptance difficulties and bullying are responsible for at least one third of the deaths by suicide of adolescents in relation to sexual orientation issues, data from DATASUS indicate that in Brazil, for every 100,000 inhabitants between 15 and 19 years the suicide

mortality rate is 4 for men and 2 for women. However, men when trying to commit suicide are more successful compared to women, due to the typology of suicide, although women try more against life, thus observing that sexual orientation is related to suicide symptoms (SILVA; RODINI, 2012).

Sousa et al., (2011) states that the process of changing a person towards sexual orientation is not easy, in which the hegemonic heterosexual pattern predominates in professional assistance based on prejudice and discrimination, which can thus generate institutional homophobia and put at risk the rights of citizens, leading to the removal of health services for LGBT people. On the other hand, government policies have been fighting homophobia, where the general objective of the national LGBT health policy is to eliminate any and all forms of prejudice and discrimination, aiming to reduce inequality both in society and in the consolidation of the principles of SUS

Of the articles selected for research, most of them addressed the family environment and homosexuality as a central theme, with prejudice and homophobia being a background, or something directed in the background, or even just mentioned in the studies. It is emphasized here that, based on what was found, further discussion is needed through research on family and social acceptance of homosexuals as a real object of studies, emphasizing the risks of non-acceptance of homosexuality to the family and society, as the eradication of parenteral and social homophobia.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

In view of the study presented, it is possible to conclude that homosexuality is known since the dawn of humanity, being studied from the beginning of the twentieth century, obtaining, then, several definitions until the present day. Over the years, homosexuals come in search of more space in society, even with several barriers faced.

It appears that one of the problems for confronting prejudice begins in the home environment itself, being in the vast

majority heterosexist. A barrier then occurs when the child decides to reveal his/her sexual orientation, as he/she is faced with an environment of rejection, the parents are faced with the “destruction” of the dream of a so-called traditional family. Thus, the first barrier for homosexuals to assume their gender identity arises. Added to family traditionalism we have the religious issue.

There are many obstacles to be faced by homosexuals, not just family rejection and in some cases religious intolerance, they still have to face a certain prejudice and homophobia sometimes veiled in part of society. Homophobia is demonstrated with verbal abuse, even generating physical aggression, which may have consequences without return, such as depression, suicide and homicide .

Homosexual acceptance is something that encompasses several difficulties, and homosexuals need support from health services, especially psychological support, in an attempt to face their internal and external conflicts.

Although homosexuality is currently a popular topic, no publications were found regarding nurses’ interventions in the context of homosexual acceptance, not even regarding differentiated reception for this public.

In relation to the researched studies, it is concluded that the specific intervention of the nurse professional to welcome the homosexual in the process of own and family acceptance are scarce, as there are still several constraints and other types of problems, such as the lack of preparation of professionals. Therefore, it is clear that there is a need to deepen the theme, mainly with research directed to nursing. An implementation of permanent education actions in the health of the LGBT population would help to combat prejudice, carry out campaigns in order to show the population sexual diversity together with the permanent training of professionals.

REFERENCES

ARRIAL, Y. P., CENTENARO, D. L Personal

and family experiences of female homosexuals . Psychology in Study Journal , vol. 13, no. 4, p. 771-77 2008

ALBINO, C.B; et al. Life trajectory of a homosexual: between silence and oppression . Science Care and Health Magazine , vol. At the. 64, pp.424-432. 2007.

BARCELOS, TS BATISTA, JSS Between revealing and hiding: parents and children in the face of the discovery of homosexuality . Latin American Magazine , no.17, p.124-148. 2014.

BRAZIL, Ministry of Health. Take good care of everyone’s health. 2016 . Comprehensive health care for gay and bisexual men.

BRAZIL, IBGE. Demographic census . 2010. Available at: www.ibge.gov.br

GARCIA, A. MOULIN, ES Sexuality and work: a study on discrimination against male homosexuals in the banking sector . Public Administration Magazine , Vol.44, no.6, p. 1353-77. 2010.

GONSALVES, LT SILVA, FTF Familial homophobia: Opening the closet ‘between four walls. 2013. Available at : http://pepsic.bvsalud.org/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S180952672013000300005 .

HAUER , M. SIQUEIRA, RG Mothers, Children and Homosexuality: Narratives of Acceptance . Themes in Psychology Magazine , Vol. 23, no. 3, p. 649-662. 2015 _

MAGRINI, MLS; et al. Family and Sexual Orientation: Difficulties in Accepting Male Homosexuality . Journal Themes in Psychology Vol. 23, no. 3, 677-692. 2014.

MOREIRA, F. MARTINS, M. Homosexuality and its history . ETIC Magazine - Scientific Initiation Meeting . vol. 4, 2008. Available at: <http://intertemas.unitoledo.br/revista/index.php/ETIC/article/viewFile/1646/1569> .

NOGUEIRA, CAO; et al. (In)Conditional Parental Love: Study on the Influence of Perceived Parental Acceptance/Rejection

in Homosexuals, Lesbians and Bisexuals. 2012. Available at: [https://www.rea.pt/imgs/uploads/doc-estudos-2012-amor-parental-\(in\)conditional.pdf](https://www.rea.pt/imgs/uploads/doc-estudos-2012-amor-parental-(in)conditional.pdf) .

OTTOSSON, D. Homophobia of the State . 2007. Available at: <https://issuu.com/lesbrujas/docs/ilgahomofobiadeestado2009> .

PAGANO, LPM Homosexuality and the historiography and trajectory of the homosexual movement. 2011. Available at: www.uel.br/revistas/uel/index.php/antiteses/article/download/7153/9668 .

REGIS, TPN; et al. The impact of homophobia on the health of homosexual adolescents. Anna Nery School Magazine , vol.19, no.4 p.664-70. 2015.

SCARDUA, A. ALVES, ESF The Debate on Homosexuality Mediated by Social Representations: Homosexual and Heterosexual Perspectives. Psychol. reflex Crit . vol.19 no.3. 2006.

SILVA, FT F, RONDINI. CA Ideations and suicide attempt in an adolescent with hetero and homoerotic sexual practices . Revista Saúde Sociedade , v.21, n.3, p.651-667 2012

SOUSA, PJ Humanization in welcoming lesbians, gays, bisexuals, transvestites and transsexuals in primary care: bioethical reflections for nursing . Nursing Journal UFPE on line . vol. 5 no.4, p.1064-071. 2011.

SOARES CB, HOGA LAK, PEDUZZI M, SANGALETI C, YONEKURA TS, SILVA DRAD. Integrative review: concepts and methods used in nursing. Rev Esc Enferm USP [internet]. 2014; [cited 2016 Nov 03]; 48(2):335-45.

ZUCCHI, AMM GARCIA, GMD The Voice of the Secret: Homosexuality in the Family. 1999. Available at: www.domusterapia.com.br/site/files/PF1ZucchiDocolas.pdf .